

IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY OF DEVELOPMENT OF THE MUSICAL CULTURE OF CHILDREN OF PRESCHOOL AGE

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Abstract. *This article talks about how musical education is implemented in the preschool education system of Uzbekistan. In particular, the role and importance of music in the development of children was discussed in preschool education, where children receive musical education from a young age.*

Keywords: *music, preschool education, aesthetics, taste, perfection, method.*

INTRODUCTION

President Shavkat Mirziyoyev said: "... if we do not restore our culture, tomorrow there will be no progress in the country, in the people, in the age without spiritual nourishment." From the adoption of a number of decrees and decisions in this area, it is possible to understand how important music is in the education of young people. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-6000 dated 26.05.2020 "On measures to further increase the role and influence of culture and art in the life of society", 02.02.2022 The decision No. PQ-112 of 2011 "On additional measures for the further development of the sphere of culture and art" is the basis for the development of the sphere [2].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Music - aesthetic education, should become a component of the work carried out in the way of educating a person of a democratic society. Types of education in Uzbekistan [4]:

- Pre-school education and training;
- General secondary and secondary special education;
- Professional education;
- Higher education;
- Post-higher education;
- Retraining of personnel and improvement of their qualifications;
- Education outside of school. Music plays a leading role in the preschool education system where children receive education and training.

Preschool education and training is a type of education aimed at teaching and educating children, developing them intellectually, spiritually, morally, ethically, aesthetically and physically, as well as preparing children for general secondary education [4].

Preschool education and upbringing also includes one-year compulsory preparation for primary education for children aged six to seven years. Interest in music from a young age determines the positive qualities and aspects of a child that will need to be formed through music in the future. In preschool education and upbringing, the child is educated morally through music. His aesthetic taste, artistic creativity, world of imagination develops precisely through music education.

Regarding education, the famous Uzbek pedagogue Abdulla Awlani says: "education is for us either life or death, salvation or destruction, or happiness or disaster" (in the book "Al-Hasil"), personal education is not private, but it can be understood that it is a social and national issue. After all, the progress of every country, the power of the times, depends on the education of the generations. From this point of view, attention is paid to spiritual and moral aspects in the upbringing of young people and children.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

There are several tasks in providing musical and aesthetic education to children [5]:

- making children perceive the beauty of nature, works of art;
- formation of aesthetic taste and feeling;
- teaching to fully understand the concept of beauty in life;
- formation of children's artistic creativity;
- teaching children to bring beauty into their lives, their activities, etc.

1 Based on this, several tasks related to music in preschool education have been defined. Developing a child's musical ability.

2. Teaching children singing and musical-rhythmic skills. Cultivating their ability to perceive, feel and understand music.

3. Development of artistic and creative abilities in the child.

It is possible to teach a child to understand the meaning of music by listening to music while conducting music classes in preschool education. Performing musical-rhythmic movements is taught starting with simple hand and foot movements. Through this, it is possible to achieve the formation of the first musical rhythmic skills. Singing is mainly performed in a collective way, and during singing, children develop the competencies of proper breathing and accompaniment to musical instruments. It is desirable for children of kindergarten age to perform actions corresponding to the words in order to better understand the content of the song together with singing. It is necessary to introduce children to musical instruments in the course of music lessons in pre-school education and upbringing.

Since the child acquires knowledge and skills that will be needed throughout his life from a young age, music culture in preschool education and upbringing takes a leading place in the formation of the child's spirituality and the world of imagination. The manner in which music education is implemented in this part of the educational system will remain one of the factors that will determine the moral education, aesthetics, spirituality and culture of the future generation.

Interest in music from a young age has a strong influence on a person's further musical development, provides the formation of other skills and tastes, and cultivates a good musical taste. Music is a great source of aesthetic and spiritual mood. Taking into account the great influence of music on the child's emotions and formation, on understanding and feeling its content, the appropriate use of a musical work that correctly reflects truth and reality has a special place. The main source of the formation of musical images is directly related to the compatibility of nature and human speech, perception of beauty in the surrounding world. The tasks of organizing music lessons in preschool educational organizations are as follows:

❖ instilling love and interest in music in children of preschool age, educating primary musical taste.

❖ development of perception of music, listening ability, aesthetic taste, general culture in children of preschool age.

- ❖ development of musical ability, formation of musical taste, development of artistic creativity in children of preschool age.

- ❖ education of perception of musical works.

- ❖ methods and methods of teaching listening to music, singing, playing musical instruments, musical rhythmic movements.

- ❖ formation of musical ability, emotional attitude to music, ability to listen to music, sense of rhythm.

- ❖ formation of basic performance skills in children's music and singing, rhythmic, playing children's musical instruments activities.

- ❖ to develop general musical ability, individual skills, singing voice and expressiveness of movements.

Tasks of musical education [6]:

1. Cultivating love and interest in music.

2. Enriching children's musical experience (based on musical works).

3. Introduce children to simple musical concepts, develop skills in listening to music, singing, and musical rhythms.

4. Formation of emotional feeling in children. Cultivating a sense of melody and rhythm in them.

5. Developing musical taste (based on musical impressions).

6. Development of creativity in children (based on all activities).

Musical works should be selected taking into account the psychological characteristics of children, their interests and worldviews. The pre-school period is called early childhood in psychology and includes the most beautiful and memorable moments of childhood.

Music education is taught as part of general subjects in kindergartens and general secondary schools. Today's demand sets specific tasks for preschool educational institutions in terms of providing musical and aesthetic education: - to make children perceive the beauty of nature, works of art; - formation of aesthetic taste and feeling; - teaching to fully understand the concept of beauty in life; - formation of children's artistic creativity; - bringing beauty to children into their lives and activities. Preschool education occupies an important place in the continuous education system.

Currently, the importance of preschool educational institutions is playing an important role as the first stage of continuous education. Therefore, the importance of separate teaching of each subject is increasing.

CONCLUSION

Perception of musical works creates emotional excitement. In this state of the child, emotions appear on the basis of familiar content and joy. It is necessary to educate the ability of children to understand and accept the work.

Thus, the education of musical perception goes as follows [7]:

1. Extraction of musical material.

2. Systematization of education and training methods.

3. Using different stages of work.

4. Use of various samples of musical works.

5. Gradually becoming more complex depending on the number and form of images of a musical work.

The aesthetic and emotional environment in the world of music creates emotional comfort for the child and forms his interest in creativity. However, the effectiveness of the musical environment depends not only on external conditions, but also on communication, musical-theoretical and psychological knowledge that regulates the child's musical development.

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